

NOTES

added in the solution of amino acids in 1N caustic soda solution and water. The mixture was shaken and allowed to stand in ice.

scientists of the C.D.R.I. Lucknow. The award of a U.G.C. research scholarship and a research grant to one of us (S.S.) is also gratefully acknowledged.

S. No.	Amino acid	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Analysis%	
				Found	Required
1.	Glycine	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ NBr ₂	171	C 30.2 H 2.0 N 4.01	C 30.9 H 1.98 N 3.96
2.	Leucine	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₄ Br ₂	160	C 39.1 H 3.6 N 3.4	C 39.7 H 3.3 N 3.1
3.	Lysine	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₄	115	C 34.4 H 2.5 N 3.3	C 34.1 C 2.0 N 3.1
4.	Isoleucine	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ NO ₄ Br ₂	Above 260	C 38.2 H 3.5 N 3.2	C 38.2 H 3.6 N 3.6
5.	Valine	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₄ Br ₂	Above 240	C 36.2 H 3.1 N 3.3	C 36.4 H 3.2 N 3.5
6.	Alanine	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₄ Br ₂	Black on 235	C 32.4 H 2.6 N 3.9	C 32.6 H 2.8 N 3.8
7.	Methionine	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₄ Br ₂	155	C 33.6 H 3.2 N 4.0	C 33.7 H 3.0 N 3.6
8.	Glutamine	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂	185	C 33.5 H 2.9 N 6.0	C 33.9 H 2.8 N 6.6
9.	Glutamic acid	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₆ NBr ₂	188	C 34.0 H 2.2 N 3.4	C 33.8 H 2.5 N 3.2
10.	Asparagine	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂	142	C 32.5 H 2.5 N 3.6	C 32.2 H 2.4 N 3.4
11.	Cysteine	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₄ NSBr ₂	140	C 30.2 H 2.4 N 4.0	C 30.0 H 2.2 N 3.8

All the melting points are uncorrected.

The liquid was filtered and the clear filtrate was extracted with ether to remove the unchanged azide. It was then acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The acid formed during the reaction was immediately extracted with ethyl acetate in which it was soluble at room temperature. The ethyl acetate was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the excess of solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. On concentration the solid separated.

Following the above procedure a number of derivatives with amino acids were obtained and are given in the table above :

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References

1. S. SAXENA and C.N. HAKSAR, *Journal of Jiwaji University*, Gwalior, 1976, IV, 36.
2. S. SAXENA and C. N. HAKSAR, *Journal of Jiwaji University*, 1976, IV, 45.
3. LELLMANN and GROTHMANN, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2728.
4. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 1481.
5. ULLMAN and KOPETSCHNI, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 428 ; Cf. LASSAR CONH and SCHULZEE, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3294.
6. *Peratone Gazette*, 1886, 16, 416, 418, 422.
7. C. N. HAKSAR and R. V. WANKHADE, *J. Vik. Univ.* 1962, 6, 67
8. CAHOURS, *Annalen*, 1840-44, 52, 328.

A new Method for Determination of Solubility Product of Silver Bromide

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WHEN two solutions of uni-univalent electrolytes having a common ion and same concentration have a junction then both Henderson's and Planck's equations for liquid junction potential (E_L) give

the same value ; $E_L = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{A_1}{A_2}$ where A_1 and A_2 are equivalent conductance of the two electrolytes. Specific conductance κ_1 and κ_2 can take the place of A_1 and A_2 in this equation. This equation is also known as Lewis and Sargent equation. A good account of liquid junction potential is given in MacInnes "Principles of Electrochemistry, 1939 edition, Chapter 13." In an electrochemical cell of the type,

the liquid junction potential can be eliminated (on the basis of the above equation), if κ_1 is made equal to κ_2 by taking (a) a mixture of two uni-univalent electrolytes of concentrations c_1 and c_2 having a common ion on one side of the junction and (b) one uni-univalent electrolyte of concentration c on the other side having the common ion. Now κ_1 can be made equal to κ_2 and the concentration of the common ion kept the same on two sides of the junction by making $c=c_1+c_2$ and $A_c=A_1c_1+A_2c_2$. c , c_1 and c_2 denote the concentrations (gm.mole/litre) of silver nitrate, sodium nitrate and potassium nitrate respectively. Further A , A_1 and A_2 denote the equivalent conductances of silver nitrate, sodium nitrate and potassium nitrate at $\mu=c$.

There is no general equation connecting equivalent conductance and temperature. Equivalent conductance at all temperatures are not recorded in literature. In the small region of temperature in which the work was done, equivalent conductance of the three salts varies linearly with temperature. So there was no difficulty in finding the required values of A , A_1 and A_2 at the concerned temperatures. No value of μ was selected for which A , A_1 , A_2 and were not known at a number of temperatures.

The above cell has been used in determining the solubility product of silver bromide at 45°.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water from G.R. quality salts at the experimental temperature. Silver-silver bromide electrode was prepared on a platinum spiral depositing silver electrolytically¹ and bromidising in 0.1N KBr solution².

Fig 1

The solution in L.H.S. half cell was saturated with thoroughly washed silver bromide to prolong the life of the electrode. The electrode vessels, bridge and setting up of the cells were similar to that described earlier³. Temperature was $45 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer was used. Duplicate cells invariably used generally agreed within 0.15 mv., difference going up to 0.2mv. in a few cases. The experimental results are given in the following table.

TABLE-1

c_1 NaNO ₃	c_2 KNO ₃	E in abs. volt	$E - \frac{RT}{F} \ln c + \frac{2.3026RT}{F} A \sqrt{\mu}$
0.00377	0.00123	0.21180	0.35941
0.00790	0.00210	0.22945	0.35904
0.01500	0.00500	0.24765	0.35963
0.04166	0.00834	0.27035	0.35995
0.05923	0.01077	0.27880	0.36055
0.08080	0.01920	0.28715	0.36084

Discussion

Charges on the ions may be left out. Let a_{Ag} and f indicate the activity and activity coefficient respectively of Ag^+ in silver nitrate solution and let a^*A_g and a^*B_r indicate the activity of Ag^+ and Br^- in the mixture of sodium nitrate and potassium nitrate. We may assume that up to $\mu=0.1$, $a^*A_g = a^*B_r$ and $\log f_1 = -A\sqrt{\mu} + \beta_1 \mu$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The e.m.f. of the cell } E &= \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{Ag}}{a^*A_g} \\ &= \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{cf}{a^*A_g} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{cf}{\sqrt{k_{sp}}} \\ \text{or, } E - \frac{RT}{F} \ln c + \frac{2.3026RT}{F} A \sqrt{\mu} &= \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \cdot \beta_1 \mu \\ &\quad - \frac{2.3026RT}{2F} \log k_{sp} \end{aligned}$$

Plot (Fig 1) of L.H.S. (denoted by p) of the above equation against μ is a straight line from which the value of k_{sp} comes out to be 4.101×10^{-12} . When converted to molality scale, it becomes 4.182×10^{-12} against Owen and Brinkley's⁴ value of 4.055×10^{-12} Gledhill and Malan's⁵ value of 4.56×10^{-12} and our own value⁶ by Owen's method⁷ of 3.910×10^{-12} , all on molality scale. Hence the present method is useful.

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References

1. "Reference Electrodes", Edited by Ives and Janz; 1961 Ed. p. 205.
2. E. A. MAC WILLIAM and A. R. GORDON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 984.
3. S. NATH, S. ADITYA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 28, 683.
4. B. B. OWEN and S. R. BRINKLEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2233.
5. J.A. GLEDHILL and G. McP. MALAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 126.
6. A. C. JHA and B. PRASAD, Ph.D. Thesis, Patna University, 1972.
7. B. B. OWEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2229.

Gravimetric Determination of Selenium with Phenylhydrazine

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LITERATURE provides a number of reagent¹⁻⁵ for the gravimetric determination of selenium. In most of the procedures recommended, selenium is precipitated as its red variety and must be dried cautiously for 4-6 hr before final weighing. Hydroxylamine method is more suitable for selenium but is still not attractive because of the long time needed for digestion. Hovorka⁶ employed hydrazine hydrate in perchloric and hydrochloric acids and reports that the determination of selenium in perchloric acid was unsatisfactory. However, Ooba and Uneo⁷ studied this reaction in perchloric acid for determining selenium in chalcogenide materials, prescribed a minimum of 4 hr digestion at boiling water bath temperature. This paper describes an accurate and relatively rapid gravimetric method for selenium.

Phenylhydrazine has been used very largely as a reagent for the characterisation of carbohydrates. The use of this reagent for the analytical determination of metals has been very limited. It has been

applied for the determination of micro amounts of selenium colorimetrically⁸. Using this the reduction of selenious acid into elementary selenium is accomplished in both tartaric and hydrochloric acid solutions in about 30 min.

Unlike the existing methods the procedure now proposed is rapid and can be completed in about 2 hr.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical purity.

Selenium Solution: A standard solution was prepared by dissolving 1.6329 g of selenious acid (BDH AnalaR 2 grade) in one litre of double distilled water. The amount of selenium was determined using hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁹.

Reagent Solution: 10 ml of phenylhydrazine was dissolved in 100 ml of rectified spirit.

Recommended Procedure: An aliquot of selenium solution (containing 9.90-99.00 mg of C) was transferred to a 400 ml beaker. To this, tartaric acid (20 g) and appropriate amount of reagent solution (1 ml=20 mg Se) were added. The solution was brought to a final volume of 200 ml with distilled water. The beaker was placed on a boiling water bath and heated for 30 min till the black elemental selenium separated. It was then filtered through a G-4 sintered glass crucible, washed free from excess phenylhydrazine with alcohol and dried at 120° to constant weight. The results are listed in Table 1.

TABLE—1a. DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM
Tartaric Acid 20 g; Reagent solution, 5 ml.

Amount of Selenium taken mg	Amount of Selenium found mg	Recovery %
99.00	98.90	99.9
49.50	49.40	99.8
49.50	49.45	99.9
24.75	24.70	99.8
9.90	9.88	99.8

TABLE—1b. DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM IN HYDROCHLORIC ACID (2.0 N)

Amount of Selenium taken mg	Amount of Selenium found mg	Recovery %
10.54	10.50	99.8
21.08	21.14	100.2
31.62	31.58	99.9
42.16	42.16	100.0
52.70	52.64	99.9
63.24	63.18	99.9
84.32	84.12	99.8
115.94	115.94	100.0
126.48	126.28	99.8
147.56	147.68	100.1